

Modeling Disease-Associate T-cells Distribution

Gal Passi^{1*}, Amir Weinfeld^{1*}, Dina Schneidman-Duhovny¹

¹ The Hebrew University of Jerusalem, School of Computer Science and Engineering, Jerusalem, Israel

gal.passi@mail.huji.ac.il, dina.schneidman@mail.huji.ac.il, *Equal Contribution

T-cells play a central role in adaptive immunity and are implicated in numerous human pathologies. Their function relies primarily on the hypervariable complementarity-determining region 3 (CDR3), a short sequence (~12-18 amino acids) crucial for peptide recognition. Identifying and generating disease-associated T-cells holds significant potential in personalized medicine, yet despite advances in sequencing technologies, known disease-associated TCR sequences remain limited.

Here, we propose an unsupervised generative approach to model the distribution of CDR3 sequences associated with multiple sclerosis (MS), curating a dataset of 73 patients and 152 healthy subjects from TCRdb. Pathological CDR3 sequences are isolated from a repertoire of patients' blood samples by identifying sequences enriched in patients relative to a healthy background model. Sequences commonly found in healthy individuals are subsequently removed. To enhance the training dataset, we incorporate closely related sequences that differ by a single amino acid substitution from the naive set (Fig. 1A).

We demonstrate that a transformer model, trained on our curated dataset, effectively discriminates between patient and healthy controls (Fig. 1B), achieving good predictive capabilities (TPR=0.90, TNR=0.81, FPR=0.19, FNR=0.10) While a recent work by Zaslavsky et al (2025) demonstrated a diagnostic potential of using genetic data from B and T cells in other diseases, our sequence only approach employs a fully generative method. Confident positive sequences identified (Fig. 1B) are used to train a variational autoencoder (VAE), effectively capturing the MS-associated CDR3 sequence distribution. Sequence representations distinctly separate MS-associated sequences from naive circulating T-cells (Fig. 1C), capturing a disease-specific sub-distribution. Generative approaches have broad applications in designing personalized immunotherapies such as CAR-T cells. Our proposed pipeline can be readily adapted to other diseases.

Figure 1. *A. Graphs represent the ratio of repeating sequences (y-axis log scale) in increasing numbers of patients and healthy subjects. Shades represent a 95% confidence interval. Dashed line - significant sequence enrichment difference ($k^*=3$, p -value < 0.0001). **Top right** schematic representation of sequence processing pipeline. D^* - sequences repeating in $\geq k^*$ patients. H sequences repeating in ≥ 3 healthy subjects. ID , IH - inflation process to sequences 1-edit distance away. Gray areas represent sequences intersecting with the healthy set which are removed during preprocessing. **B.** Aggregated probabilities of blood-drawn CDR3 sequences as predicted by our trained transformer on a test set consisting of eight MS patients and eleven healthy subjects. Scores closer to 1 are predicted to be related to MS. Orange and blue dotted lines represent the mean values of a Gaussian Mixture Model used for patient classification - trained on the train-set sequence distribution. Gray area represents confident MS-related sequences used to train the downstream VAE. **C.** Dimensionality reduction (PCA) of test-set CDR3 sequences. Transparent dots represent low-confidence sequences (scores < 0.75) as predicted by our trained CDR3-transformer.*